

A Study on the Total Quality Management Practices Among SMEs in India

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K. Mohanasundaram

*Assistant Professor, Department of Operations Management
Alliance University, Bengaluru*

Abstract

Today's business environment and the nature of the term quality itself imply that the quality concept is an ever-changing one. Hence, continuous attention should be paid to catch up with the ever-changing quality standards to control moving targets in an internationally competitive market. Quality initiatives have been a part of an organization strategy irrespective of the size of the organization. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) have been playing a vital role in the growth process of the Indian economy since independence despite strong competition from the bigger sector. In a developing country like India, the role and importance of SMEs are very significant towards poverty eradication, employment generation, rural development, and creating regional balance in the promotion and growth of various development activities. Next to the agriculture sector, SMEs contributing a significant percentage to the GDP and employability. However, due to liberalization, globalization, changes in the manufacturing strategies, technological changes, and empowered customers and dynamic market scenarios, SMEs are facing a challenging competition. The competitive advantage for a firm to sustain in the market are – price, quality, flexibility (customization) and on-time delivery. To produce a quality product and increase productivity, a firm must practice the Total Quality Management concept into its product development process to confront the challenges of global competition. The objective of this study is to understand the awareness level among the SMEs related to the elements of TQM, to identify the critical success factors in the implementation of TQM in the SMEs and main challenges to implement the same in their organization. The expected outcome is to establish the relationship between the factors and organizational performance.

Keywords: Total Quality Management, Small and Medium Enterprises, awareness, and critical success factor.

Introduction

Quality has been considered as a market variable of prime prominence after the success of Japanese organizations in the late 20th century. The realization that superior quality is critical to the functioning of operations that led to a need for integrating “Total Quality Management” (TQM) as a strategic choice in the organization. It had emerged as an essential business management strategy, and implementation of Total Quality Management (TQM) at all levels had become a source of competitive advantage for the organizations. TQM has evolved through four main stages identified as Quality Inspection, Quality Assurance, Quality control, and TQM. TQM is the way of managing an enterprise toward achieving business excellence (Dahlgaard et al., 1998)

Business/ competitive strategy/ Quality and TQM

In today's globalized economy quality management and control is recognized as the foundation of business competitiveness and is proactively integrated into all business. Many companies are trying very hard not only to satisfy the customer's needs; but this can be achieved through cost reduction, improvement in product performance, increased customer satisfaction, and a constant effort towards world-class organizations. Many companies understand that TQM is necessary to remain competitive, to retain market share, and respond to change in demand. Small and Medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) have been slow in adopting TQM when compared to larger companies; very few had advanced. Globalization is driving companies toward quality as a necessary tool to compete successfully in worldwide markets. A direct outcome of this new emphasis is the philosophy of total quality management (TQM). In essence, TQM is a companywide perspective that strives for customer satisfaction by seeking zero defects in products and services.

The Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) sector has emerged as a highly vibrant and dynamic sector of the Indian economy over the last five decades. It contributes significantly to the economic and social development of the country by fostering entrepreneurship and generating more employment opportunities at comparatively lower capital cost, next only to agriculture. SMEs are complementary to large industries as ancillary units, and this sector contributes significantly to the inclusive industrial development of the country. SMEs are widening their domain across sectors of the economy, producing a diverse range of products and services to meet demands of domestic as well as global markets. Worldwide, the maximum numbers of firms are SMEs, and they play a vital role in the economy. SMEs have a direct impact on economic development in both developed and developing countries. SMEs are at the center of interest since the quality debate for several reasons. One is that larger organizations will not be able to improve the quality of their product, services, and process unless their suppliers or the second-tier suppliers also grow to a higher level of quality maturity. One believes that the adoption of TQM in SMEs is a must, a gradual progression, and selection of appropriate "quality tools and initiatives" as and when necessary, with the ultimate aim of continuous improvement in the organization.

Definition of MSME: By the provision of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises Development (MSMED) Act, 2006 the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) are classified as below

Table 1

Manufacturing sector	
Enterprise category	Investment in plant and machinery
Micro enterprises	Does not exceed twenty five lakhs rupees
Small enterprises	More than twenty five lakhs but not exceed five crores rupees
Medium enterprises	More than five crores but not exceed ten crores rupees
Service sector	
Enterprise category	Investment in equipment
Micro enterprises	Does not exceed ten lakhs rupees
Small enterprises	More than ten lakhs but not exceeding two crore rupees
Medium enterprises	More than two crores but not exceeding five crore rupees

Organizational performance and Total Quality Management

Organizational performance has several meanings dependent upon the perspective and discipline from which the scholar articulates this concept. Organizational performance is conceived as organizational output or productivity. TQM perspective of productivity considers both the

qualitative and quantitative facets of relationship between inputs and outputs. There is empirical evidence that lends credence to the relationship between TQM and organizational Performance. Hendrick and Singal (1997) investigated the relationship between quality of product and financial performance. Garvin (1991) conducted a study on the impact of TQM practices and organizational performance and found a strong relationship measured in terms of productivity, profitability, and customer relations.

Review of Literature

Most manufacturing enterprises throughout the world are SME dependent on their domestic markets to develop their business (Day, 2000; Freeman, 2000). Compared with large enterprises, SMEs product mostly is the result of labor-intensive production, not those based on high technology and automation. They are, however, more flexible in their organizations and management that large organization because of their small vertical organizational structure (Ghobadian & Gallear, 1996). No complex, financial, production or specialized management is needed, so they are not able to make rapid progress in achieving their goals once they are committed. (Sonthithai & Thavornbud, 2003).

Small businesses are usually constrained by their size, their lack of technical expertise, managerial time, and financial resources and their human resource limitation). Moreno-Luzon, 1993; Lee and Oakes, 1995). A study by Ahire and Gohlar (1996) found that the introduction of TQM in SMEs had helped to sharpen SMEs' market focus, to become more efficient, to harness their human resources better, and to improve their competitiveness. They also concluded that TQM implementation leads to better product quality and that SMEs can implement it as effectively as larger companies. There is a general awareness of the importance of SMEs for a country's economic growth, industrial development, and employment generation.

Many scholars study identifies relationships among QM practices and examines the effects of these practices on performance, but the finding inconsistencies and conflicting results among scholars. These findings suggest that a positive relationship exists between the QM practices or TQM and firm performance and between other variables such as product quality, product, and process performance, perceived quality, quality drivers, reduced cost, more satisfied customers, and improve financial performance. In general, a large body of literature highlights the positive impact of QM practices on performance (Zu, 2009; Kaynak, 2003; Ahire, Golhar, & Waller, 1996; Kaynak & Hartley, 2005; Sila & Ebrahimpour, 2005; Anderson, Rungtusanatham, Schroeder, & Devaraj, 1995; Flynn, Schroeder, & Sakakibara, 1995; Ho, Duffy, & Shih, 1999; Prajogo & Sohal, 2003; 2006; Terziovski & Samson, 1999; Choi & Eboch, 1998), but others have not found a relationship between QM practices –TQM- and performance (Nair, 2006; Agus, 2003).

Critical success factors (CSFs) are the factors that guarantee the successful implementation of quality management. Several studies have attempted to synthesize different QM practices into a meaningful set of CSFs to help users conceptualize QM more easily. CSFs are management practices, actions, or pre-conditions necessary for successful Quality Management (Saraph et al., 1989). Quality Management practices have been investigated extensively, e.g., Saraph et al. (1989), Flynn et al. (1994), Powell (1995), Ahire et al. (1996). Each one of these studies determined dimensions of QM that applied by organizations to gain competitive advantage.

Husband and Mandal (1999) developed the conceptual model by integrating dimensions (core, structural, fundamental, sustainability, integrative, and external dimensions) of SMEs, and this model could be used by owners, operators, managers, quality professionals, and other SME stakeholders. This conceptual model was developed to improve the implementation rate by clearly understanding and interpreting the quality methods. McAdam (2000) developed a quality

model for SMEs from the large corporate business model, and concluded that five critical success factors (CSFs) viz., business goals, management commitment, customer satisfaction, employee involvement, and performance measurement are similar for both large companies and SMEs.

Many studies have examined the positive and negative (or non-significant) relationships or correlations between TQM practices and various performance measures. An extent review of previous TQM studies on organizational performance suggests that there are various performance measures indicators (Sadikoglu and Zehir, 2010; Monge et al., 2006; Zakunan et al., 2010). Different indicators used for measuring organizational performance have been identified as quality performance (example quality of product and service, customer relations, customer satisfaction with products quality, and level of quality performance relative to industry norms)- Arumugam et al. (2008). Zakuan et al.(2010) in their study measured organizational performance through two categories which are satisfaction level (example employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction) and business results (example productivity, number of successful new products, cost performance, and profitability).

Main elements to achieve an effective organizational management processes is the performance measurement. The performance of an organization can be directly related to its ability to achieve its strategic and financial objectives (Li et al., 2006). The performance of organizations was mostly neglected in past research, whereas some others (Katou, 2008) who were discussing the organizational performance concerning to the financial performance only. Stock et al.,(2000) examined the organization's performance through measuring both financial and market harmonic performance, which includes the return on investment measures (ROI), sales profit and growth, and market share progress. The organizational performance could be measured either depending on operational performance, which is referring to the whole performance of one organization that includes financial performance, customer satisfaction and effectiveness of product quality (Brah et al., 2000). Whereas the operational performance of an organization can be directly handled with the enhanced delivery performance, flexibility, minimizing costs and errors, and enhancing process productivity (Nunnally, 1978).

Objectives

1. To find the awareness among SMEs related to the principles of Total Quality Management.
2. To identify the critical success factors in the implementation of TQM in the SMEs.
3. To find the relationship between the Critical Success Factors and organization performance.

Conceptual framework

Research Methodology

This section discusses the research design, research instruments, and its administration, sample, and data collection procedures used in the study.

The research methodology is essential, as it guide the researchers on the steps needs to be taken to accomplish the objectives of the research (Tsang and Antony, 2001; Antony et al., 2002). In this research study, a questionnaire survey methodology was adopted in selected SMEs in India.

The study uses both descriptive and inferential research. Descriptive analysis intends to present facts concerning the nature and status of a situation, as it exists at the time of the study. The present study uses a **descriptive cross-sectional study design**. It is concerned with the analysis of opinions and demographic information. A structured questionnaire was used to collect the primary data. This study utilizes electronic mail (e-mail) survey method, and personal interaction with the executives of the SME's , as the means of data collection. By reviewing the literature on quality management initiatives in SMEs, the survey instrument was designed. It comprises of three sections, namely the demographic variables, opinion on the principles on quality management and organization performance. A sample of 68 SME's across Bangalore, Chennai, and Hyderabad was selected through snowball sampling (nonprobability sampling technique) for this study. Out of which, only 57 (84%) respondents were aware of the principles of Total Quality Management. So, the reduced sample size which, was used for the study is, 57. The profile of the business units that participated in this study comprises of Electronics and electrical, Machine tools, polymers, automobile and Spares, and Home appliances. The sample covers reasonably the representation from top management, middle, and bottom level management. Using SPSS, and Excel the data were analyzed.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Descriptive Analysis

Below table 2 represents the classification of respondents based on the type of organization.

Table 2

Type of organization	Frequency	Percentage
Electrical and Electronics	12	21%
Machine tools	07	13%
Polymers	03	5%
Home appliances	15	26%
Automobile and spares	17	30%
Others	03	5%
Total	57	

The average size of the firm (in terms of the workforce) is represented in the following Table 3. 65% of the firm has the average number of the workforce between 21 and 30, followed by 14% of the firms in the number between 15 and 20 respectively.

Table 3

Size of the firm (Average)	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 15 employees	06	11%
15-20 employees	08	14%
21-30 employees	37	65%
More than 30 employees	06	11%
Total	57	

Table 4 below represents the classification of respondents based on qualification. 47% of the respondents have graduation as a qualification, followed by ITI with 28%, respectively.

Table 4

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
ITI	16	28%
Graduation	27	47%
Post-Graduation	08	14%
Others	06	11%
Total	57	

Table 5 represents the position of the respondents in their respective organizations

Position	Number of respondents	Percentage
Top level management	17	30%
Middle level management	28	50%
Bottom level management	12	20%
Total	57	

The respondents have the average year of experience between 6 months and 13 years with a standard deviation of 1.5 years.

Reliability analysis

To test the reliability of the questionnaire, Cronbach's alpha was calculated using SPSS software and found to be 0.712.

Table 6 Descriptive Statistics on the Constructs

Variables	Description	Mean score
Strategic Management Commitment		
SMC1	The extent of effort by top management in ensuring everyone in the organization	3.61
SMC2	Effort by management in defining, measuring, and monitoring the performance measures, which are critical in meeting customer requirements.	3.72
SMC3	The extent of management's recognition to the contribution of workers or superiors concerning the development, improvement, and maintenance of quality.	3.58
SMC4	Commitment to the TQM philosophy	3.63
SMC5	Allocation of resources and time for quality improvement	3.78
SMC6	The tendency to view employees' valuable resources.	3.85
SMC7	Integrate quality in strategic planning.	3.90
SMC8	Top management ensures that every employee knows the company's mission and business objectives.	3.87
SMC9	The company fulfills its social responsibilities (such as an environmental friendly operation)	3.80

Human Resource Management/ Employee Involvement		
HRM1	The level of effectiveness and extent of employee involvement achieved in the company	3.95
HRM2	The effectiveness with which, the company aligns human resources planning and management with the company's strategic plan.	4.10
HRM3	Effectiveness of quality improvement teams in the division.	4.20
HRM4	Amount of feedback provided to employees on their performance concerning quality.	3.95
HRM5	The extent of the effectiveness of the human resource plans concerning human resources development, training, and empowerment.	3.94
HRM6	Employee encouragement for quality initiatives	3.87
Customer Focus		
CF1	Meeting customer expectations	3.98
CF2	Effective use of customer feedback	4.01
CF3	Quick respond to the customer complaints	4.20
CF4	Conducts a customer satisfaction survey frequently (at least once in a year)	3.70
Supplier Relationship Management		
SRM1	The company regularly conducts suppliers' quality audit	3.52
SRM2	Suppliers provide relevant quality records and data.	3.48
SRM3	Selection of the suppliers are based on quality rather than price.	3.74
SRM4	The company works closely with suppliers towards long term partnership and improvement.	3.64
SRM5	Involvement of the supplier in the product development processes	3.75
SRM6	The extent of thoroughness and effectiveness of the suppliers rating system	3.84
Information and Communication Systems		
ICS1	Effective customer care system	3.78
ICS2	Effective communication system	3.65
ICS3	Use of recent technology	3.69
ICS4	Effective use of data	3.74
ICS5	Documented procedures	3.67
Continuous Improvement and Innovation		
CII1	There is a quality improvement team (e.g., quality steering committee).	3.60
CII2	The usage of quality improvement tools and techniques.	3.00
CII3	The practice of continuous improvement in all its product, processes, and services.	3.50
Process Management		
PM1	The degree to which the processes and procedures are streamlined and foolproof.	3.42
PM2	The degree to which technological capability (e.g., computerization, networking of operations, etc.) are enhanced to serve customers more effectively and compete in the market	4.15
PM3	Regular tracking and maintenance of the processes that are critical to the company	3.81

PM4	Insist on developing procedures for reducing the overall service delivery times	3.74
PM5	Emphasis on measuring customer complaints by involving and taking feedback from them for service delivery improvement	4.12
Organizational Performance		
ORP1	Customer satisfaction	4.13
ORP2	Process improvement (cycle time, productivity)	3.64
ORP3	Product quality improvement	3.51
ORP4	Financial and marketplace performance	3.87

Concerning the first principle on strategic management commitment, it was observed that majority of the respondent's opinion that, integrating quality in strategic planning, ensuring that every employee should aware of the company's mission, and tendency to view employees' as valuable resources (3.9, 3.87, and 3.85) respectively. On the second principle, namely human resources management and employee involvement, it was found that having quality improvement teams, align with the human resources planning, and providing feedback to employees on their performance concerning quality (4.2, 4.1, and 3.95) respectively. Concerning to the principle on customer focus, it was observed that the majority of the respondent's opinion that, quickly respond to the customer complaints, effective use of customer feedback, and meeting the customer expectations (4.2, 4.1 and 3.98), respectively. Concerning to the principle on the supplier relationship management, the respondent's opinion was on the thoroughness and effectiveness on the supplier rating system (3.84) followed by involvement of supplier in the product development process (3.75) and selecting the suppliers based on the quality aspect rather than price (3.74) respectively. Regarding the principle on the information and communication systems, their opinion was, on an effective customer care system with 3.78, followed by the effective use of data with 3.74, and use of advanced technology with 3.69 respectively. As regard to the principle on continuous improvement and innovation, it was observed that, majority of the respondent's opine that, quality steering committee (3.6), practice on continuous improvement of all the products, processes, and services (3.5), and usage of quality improvement tools and techniques (3.0) respectively. Lastly, the construct on process management, it was observed that majority of the respondent's opinion was, on the technological capability (4.15), followed by measuring customer complaints for service improvement (4.12), and keep track on critical processes (3.81), respectively. In relation to the respondent's opinion on the organizational performance, it was observed that the mean score for the customer satisfaction (4.13), finance and marketplace performance (3.87), and process improvement (3.64) respectively.

Table 7 Descriptive statistics and raking on Quality management constructs

Constructs	Number of items	Overall Mean score	Standard deviation	Rank
Strategic management commitment	9	3.75	0.58	4
Human Resource Management / employee involvement	6	4.00	0.53	1
Customer focus	4	3.97	0.42	2
Supplier relationship management	6	3.66	0.38	6
Information and communication system	5	3.71	0.45	5
Continuous improvement and innovation	3	3.37	0.43	7
Process management	5	3.85	0.54	3
Organizational performance	4	3.79	0.37	

Above the table shows the results of descriptive statistics of quality management constructs, and the results indicated the mean of the dimensions ranged from 4.0 to 3.37. Human resources management/employee involvement has the highest average (4.0), while continuous improvement and innovation (3.37) have the lowest average. The means of all variables in the study above the scale midpoint, which is most respondents share similar opinions toward each variable in this study. Also, the standard deviation is less than one; that is - the variations in the respondent's opinion were small.

Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between the variables about total quality management principles and organizational performance.

To test whether there exists a positive relationship between the total quality management principles and organizational performance, bivariate correlation analysis was carried out at a 1% level of significance. The below table shows the relationship between the variables. It was observed that all the variables are significance at a 1% level.

Table 8 Bivariate Correlation Table for the Quality Management Constructs and Organizational Performance

	SMC	HRM	CF	SRM	ICS	CII	PM	ORP
SMC	1							
HRM	0.824	1						
CF	0.465	0.483	1					
SRM	0.456	0.417	0.395	1				
ICS	0.625	0.524	0.497	0.335	1			
CII	0.567	0.679	0.487	0.371	0.378	1		
PM	0.876	0.567	0.551	0.489	0.449	0.769	1	
ORP	0.761	0.785	0.658	0.457	0.528	0.479	0.654	1

** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2 tailed)

Finding

- Only 84% of the respondents are aware of the principles of total quality management.
- Among the seven factors considered for the study, Human resources Management/employee involvement dominates as the critical factor for the organizational performance, followed by the customer focus.
- Continuous improvement and innovation occupy the least important among the factors considered for the study.
- Organization performance having importance on the customer satisfaction, followed by the finance and marketplace performance and process improvement, which includes reduction of cycle time and productivity.
- There is a high positive correlation between the strategic management commitment and human resources management.
- A Company should align human resources planning and management with the company's strategic plan.
- A Company should provide feedback to employees on their performance concerning quality.
- The organization should give more emphasis on the TQM training imparted to its personnel in such a way to improve and sustain the current practices of TQM.
- A TQM result does not get overnight, and to some extent, the results are intangible. It is an endless journey and needs proper direction and motivation.

Limitations

The scope of the study is limited to the manufacturing industry among SME sectors in India. Limited sample size has restricted rigorous statistical analysis as well as generalizability.

Conclusion

The environment in the current market is changing continuously, due to more competitors offering the same products and services with same quality and price. To compete with competitors, and to dominate in the market, a firm has to adopt it and manage the whole organizational strategies in more efficient and effective ways. In this regard, TQM should widely be implemented to produce remarkable results, such as improved product and service quality, enhanced productivity, reduced costs, and satisfying customer requirements. Identifying the CSF for the implementation of TQM will lead to the success. Three critical success factors identified are- Human resources management, which includes employee involvement, customer focus, and process management. SMEs need to invest more to enhance employee skills in a continuous basis. TQM is an approach to doing business that attempts to maximize the competitiveness of an organization through the continual improvement of the quality of its product, process, people, services, and environment. Thus, internalizing quality programs in an organization to improve quality and maintain a competitive edge is an enormous task.

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